

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS IN CLASSROOM AND EXTRACURRICULAR TIME

Joldasbaeva Malika

Student for the English Department,
Teachers` Training State Institute of Nukus, Uzbekistan

Annotation: *Recent trends in methodology reflect the vital role of the education sector as a whole with its internalization of the educational process, emphasis on quality, and the expansion of the use of new technologies. Theory and methods are constantly evolving in the field of ELT. The article presents well-known trends in ELT, which have been used almost recently all over the world. New trends in foreign language teaching are becoming known as GTM, the communicative method.*

Keywords: *innovative methods, innovative technologies, educational process, cooperative learning, ICT, ELT*

The new technologies mentioned in the article relate to both the methodology and the materials used in language teaching. The article discusses educational trends, new and existing methods, new teaching design, modern devices necessary for changes, the role of ICT in teaching English. The teaching of English has undergone huge changes over the years, especially over the last ten years. Previously, pupils and students were burdened with the study and assimilation of material in the framework of lectures with a selection of relevant information from prescribed texts. Currently, such alternative approaches as the development of communication, technical skills, interpersonal communication skills, ICT literacy, are becoming increasingly important. The need for successful graduates who are able to compete in the tough environment of the survival of the world market is very much in demand today.

Communicative learning

The method of communicative learning is more student-oriented and takes less time. The quality of teaching is better, and students' applied communication in English can be effectively cultivated, which means that students' communicative competence will be successfully developed.

Ideally, language in education is usually based on such a naturally acquired language ability, which, being enriched by literacy, turns into a tool for abstract thinking and academic knowledge acquisition. Teachers use various texts in English for translation, listening and grammar tests. With the proliferation of tablets and smartphones, it is believed that the textbook will disappear in a few years.

Realizing the need for transformation: English teachers convene various types of conferences and seminars to create a platform and get acquainted with the upcoming ideologies in ELT, as well as to improve their professional level.

Academic qualifications alone cannot help teachers grow professionally, on the other hand, they should be equipped with modern materials. There were too many methods of teaching English. Global globalization is inseparable from teaching English is the development of information and communication technologies. New trends in English language teaching, such as an interactive approach, are developing as a result of constant research.

Web-based training

Web-based learning is one of the fastest growing areas. There are thousands of web-based English classes that offer instruction in various basic language skills, such as learning, speaking, reading and writing, in interactive ways. Some common technologies are as follows: students can correspond with native speakers language using email by creating a personal email account (gmail, yahoo, hotmail, etc.), which is free. Students can mail their homework to teachers and get it verified. The teacher can create his own blog.

A blog is a personal or professional magazine that is frequently updated for public consumption. Blogs allow you to upload and link files that are very suitable for use as online personal journals for students. A blog becomes communicative and interactive when participants assume multipleroles, as readers/reviewers who

respond to other authors' posts, and as reader writers who, by returning to their own posts, respond to criticism of their own posts. Readers, in turn, can comment on what they read, although blogs can also be hosted in secure environments. Laptops with cameras have audio functions and technological tools. Students can communicate with their teachers and friends who are far away.

New generation devices

This year's Consumer Electronics Show (CES), held in Las Vegas, gave an idea of innovative devices designed exclusively for students. These exhibits ranged from 3D printers to smartwatches. The requirements of young people are met by new devices that allow them to study, communicate on social networks, travel and be mobile. Media streaming devices such as Google chrome cast and Roku, make group studies interactive and presentations amazing. One of the devices can broadcast media to a smart TV using a key. Another device – an e-book - is a boon for a new generation living in motion. The brand new kindle white paper is another invention. Portable Document Scanner is a great application that sorts Flatbet photos and notebook. Other devices are voice recorders, such as Olympus, can be used to record all lectures in English and playback at a convenient time. New ones have been developed language programs, educational programs for the effective development of students' skills.

A clear description of the content in terms of linguistic competence, sociolinguistic competence and pragmatic competence constitutes language. With the help of descriptor scales, the level of a student's language proficiency is measured. Descriptors consist of a number of can do statements that have received a lot of attention. In the process of teaching and learning, special attention is also paid to the involvement of students and the empowerment of teachers.

The role of the modern teacher

Researchers have defined the term "role" as a technical term that originally came from sociology and refers to the general concept of how an individual should behave. Several techniques distinguish different roles for a language teacher. In some, the role of the teacher is a part of the design, a component of the method. In

others, he is an intermediary in teaching, a supervisor, a class teacher, a consultant, and sometimes a co-communicator with students. For the third, the teacher plays the role of controller, organizer, evaluator, promoter, participant, resource, mentor and observer. The task of modern teaching is communicative language teaching.

Experimental training or practical training as the basic conceptual basis of TBLT.

Task-based language teaching (TBLT), also known as task-based instruction (TBI), focuses on using authentic language and asking students to perform meaningful tasks using the target language. Such tasks may include visiting a doctor, conducting an interview, or Contacting customer support for TBLT breaks down the barriers of the traditional class, because in TBLT. The role of the student is changing significantly. The teacher becomes a true mediator, a teacher for exclusively dialogical communication. The role of the teacher is not completely avoided, but is limited: the teacher must be a guide on the side. The role of the teacher is a leading, independent participant, analyst, advisor and manager for group data processing.

All over the world, information technologies are radically changing the ways of teaching and the activities of students, teachers and staff. The traditional method placed great emphasis on the teacher himself and was teacher-oriented. Repetitive practice, mechanical exercises and memorization were the hallmarks of traditional methods. The quality of teaching depended on how well the teacher taught. Modern trends and methods of ELT assessment aim to transfer information or knowledge into the minds of students.

References:

1. Almekhlafi A. Влияние компьютерного обучения языку (CALL) на успеваемость и отношение учащихся школ EFL Объединенных Арабских Эмиратов // Journal of Interactive Learning Research. – 2006. – №17 (2). – С. 121–142.
2. Современные тенденции в преподавании английского языка по Ен Ким // Журнал обучения английскому языку. Трехгодичное издание по изучению преподавания английского языка. –2011. – Т. 1.

3. Г.Абылова. "Проектирование учебного процесса в информационной образовательной среде, основанной на использовании средств ИКТ" // Бердах атындағы КМУ "Хабаршы" журналы. №4, 2020 йил. 103-106 с

4. Culture in Second Language Teaching and Learning; Cambridge University Press – M., 2011. – 262 с.